

Environmental Awareness Model for Students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia

Desy Safitri, Budiaman, Henita Rahmayanti, Arita Marini, Apri Wahyudi
Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Indonesia
desysafitri@unj.ac.id

Abstract

This study is aimed at proposing environmental awareness model for students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia. This survey study distributed the questionnaires to 175 students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia. Data analysis in this study used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The result of this study found that environmental awareness model for students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia proposed was good fit for the data. This study confirmed that student having noble values of sustainability has significantly positive association with student environmental awareness. However, the relationships between student environmental practices and student environmental attitudes with the student environmental awareness were not supported in this study. In the conclusion, it is highlighted that the model of environmental awareness hypothesized in this study can be implemented for students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia specifically for the association between student having noble values of sustainability and student environmental awareness.

Keywords: *Environmental awareness, noble values, sustainability*

1. Introduction

Environmental awareness indicated by the level of knowledge about the environment can be improved through a training program (Tor, 2009; Meiboudi, Karimzadegan, & Khalilnejad, 2011; Basri, Zain, Jaafar, Basri, & Suja, 2012; Viorica & Torii, 2013; Safitri, Umasih, Ibrahim, Sujarwo., Marini, Wahyudi, 2019; Safitri, Nuraini, Rihatno, Kaban, Marini, & Wahyudi, 2020; Safitri, Umasih, Yunaz, Marini, & Wahyudi, 2019). The level of environmental awareness was predicted by sustainable development and practices, attitudes and moral values of sustainability (Hassan, Noordin, Sulaiman, 2010). Environmental attitudes and behavior are different for students with different grades (Hasiloglu, Keles, & Aydin, 2011). Local culture is the main cause of social and environmental defects (Ahmed & Khatee, 2012). Environmental awareness was raised through musical instruments produced from waste materials (Ozturk, 2012). Environmental awareness level of female students is higher than male students (Altin, Tecer, Tecer, Altih, & Kahraman, 2014). However, most studies have not explained a more detail explanation about indicator measurement of student environmental awareness.

2. Literature review

Knowledge level about causes and effects of environmental issues was increased through education (Tor, 2009; Meiboudi, Karimzadegan, & Khalilnejad, 2011; Basri, Zain, Jaafar, Basri, & Suja, 2012; Viorica & Torii, 2013; Safitri, Umasih, Ibrahim, Sujarwo., Marini, Wahyudi, 2019; Safitri, Nuraini, Rihatno, Kaban, Marini, & Wahyudi, 2020; Safitri, Umasih, Yunaz, Marini, & Wahyudi, 2019). The concepts of environmental awareness are classified into emotional, attitude, and practices of sustainability awareness (Hassan, Noordin, Sulaiman, 2010). This study found as the class level of students increased, their positive environmental behaviors diminished (Hasiloglu, Keles, & Aydin, 2011). The local communities should be encouraged to act in conserving the environment followed by giving praise and gratitude in order that they can take more meaningful action towards environment (Ahmed & Khatee, 2012). Student creative thinking abilities to produce played instruments and environmental awareness were raised through recycling of the waste materials (Ozturk, 2012). As family income and family education level increased, student environmental

awareness also increases (Altin, Tecer, Tecer, Altih, & Kahraman, 2014). However, the previous studies have not provided indicator measurement of student environmental awareness.

Student environmental awareness may be estimated by student practices and attitudes towards environment as well as noble values of sustainability (Hassan, Noordin, Sulaiman, 2010). However, this research doesn't give detail indicator measurement of student environmental practices and attitudes as well as noble values of sustainability. The summary of relationships hypothesized is represented in a model seen in figure 1.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework of the Study

3. Method

This survey study was conducted for 175 students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia. Data collected in this research were associated with student environmental awareness. Analysis of content was done to literature of student environmental awareness involving practices and attitudes towards environment as well as noble values of sustainability (Hassan, Noordin, Sulaiman, 2010).

These dimensions of student environmental awareness were derived into the questionnaire given to 175 students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia. The four aspects of student environmental practices involve student comprehending the meanings of environmental issues, being in charge of environmental problems at one's place, discussing about environmental problems with others, and getting involved in environmental awareness activities. The four dimensions estimate student environmental attitudes are student feeling dissatisfied with air pollution, feeling dissatisfied with river pollution, appreciating biodiversity, and aware of being responsible towards environment. The indicators of student having noble values of sustainability include student trying to reduce amount of waste by collecting materials recycled, not using plastic bag to wrap things, conserving the use of electric energy, conserving the use of water supply, and composting the food residue to become fertilizer.

Analyzing data in this research used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with IBM SPSS Statistics 24 and SPSS AMOS 24 with 2017 Edition. SEM was used to predict the associations of student practices, attitudes, and having noble values of sustainability with student environmental awareness. Data collection was done from 175 students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia inputted in excel using responses with "strongly agree" scored 5, "agree" scored 4, "neutral" scored 3, "disagree" scored 2, "strongly disagree" scored 1 for positive questions, and "strongly agree" scored 1, "agree" scored 2, "neutral" scored 3, "disagree" scored 4, "strongly disagree" scored 5 for negative questions.

4. Results and Discussion

The result of the goodness of fit statistical analysis of environmental awareness model for students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia presented that Normed Fit Index (NFI) value arrived at 0.659 suggesting that the model suggested in this study is good fit. Comparative Fit Index (CFI) value attained 0.767 meaning that the model of environmental awareness proposed is good fit. Incremental Fit Index (IFI) value reached 0.778 pointing out that the model is good fit. Relative Fit Index (RFI) value achieved 0.570 indicating that the model is good fit. Based on SEM measurement result of this study, the environmental awareness model for students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia hypothesized in this study is a fit model.

Based on measurement model test of observed variables shown in table 1 and table 2, it can be presented that student having noble values of sustainability has positive association with student environmental awareness of 0.780. These values were significant at the 0.05 levels of t statistics. However, the relationships between student environmental practices and student environmental attitudes to the student environmental awareness of 0.835 and 0.619, respectively were not supported in this study. These findings were consistent with the research pointing out that student environmental awareness was predicted by noble values of sustainability (Hassan, 2010). However, this is not similar with the study found that practice and attitude towards environment promoted the student environmental awareness (Hassan, Noordin, Sulaiman, 2010).

Table 1. Measurement model test (Regression weights: Group number 1 – Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
EP	<---	EAWR	2.314	1.536	1.506	0.132	
ET	<---	EAWR	2.655	1.689	1.572	0.116	
NS	<---	EAWR	1.000				
EA4	<---	EP	1.000				
EA3	<---	EP	2.044	0.642	3.184	0.001	
EA2	<---	EP	1.775	0.557	3.185	0.001	
EA1	<---	EP	1.927	0.604	3.190	0.001	
EA8	<---	ET	1.000				
EA7	<---	ET	1.018	0.336	3.032	0.002	
EA6	<---	ET	0.458	0.253	1.810	0.040	
EA5	<---	ET	1.314	0.431	3.049	0.002	
EA13	<---	NS	1.000				
EA12	<---	NS	0.443	0.580	0.764	0.445	
EA11	<---	NS	4.686	2.570	1.824	0.048	
EA10	<---	NS	4.797	2.636	1.820	0.049	
EA9	<---	NS	6.119	3.336	1.834	0.047	

Source: AMOS Results 2019

Table 2. Measurement model test (Standardized regression weights: Group number 1 – Default model)

			Estimate
EP	<---	EAWR	0.835
ET	<---	EAWR	0.619
NS	<---	EAWR	0.780
EA4	<---	EP	0.305
EA3	<---	EP	0.609
EA2	<---	EP	0.610
EA1	<---	EP	0.615
EA8	<---	ET	0.427
EA7	<---	ET	0.485
EA6	<---	ET	0.205
EA5	<---	ET	0.497
EA13	<---	NS	0.160

EA12	<---	NS	0.073
EA11	<---	NS	0.641
EA10	<---	NS	0.618
EA9	<---	NS	0.761

Source: AMOS Results 2019

Notes:

- EAWR = environmental awareness
- EP = environmental practices
- ET = environmental attitudes
- NS = having noble values of sustainability
- EA1 = comprehending the meanings of environmental issues
- EA2 = being in charge of environmental problems at one's place
- EA3 = discussing about environmental problems with others
- EA4 = getting involved in environmental awareness activities
- EA5 = feeling dissapointed with air pollution
- EA6 = feeling dissapointed with river pollution
- EA7 = appreciating biodiversity
- EA8 = awaring of being responsibility towards environment
- EA9 = trying to reduce amount of waste by collecting materials recycled
- EA10 = not using plastic bag to wrap things
- EA11 = conserving the use of electric energy
- EA12 = conserving the use of water supply
- EA13 = composting the food residue to become fertilizer

In table 1 and table 2, it can be shown that student comprehending the meanings of environmental issues, being in charge of environmental problems at one's place, discussing about environmental problems with others, and getting involved in environmental awareness activities have significant positive association with student environmental practices of 0.615, 0.610, 0.609, and 0.305, respectively. Table 1 and table 2 indicated that student feeling dissapointed with air pollution, feeling dissapointed with river pollution, appreciating biodiversity, and awaring of being responsibility towards environment have significant positive connection with student environmental attitudes of 0.497, 0.205, 0.485, and 0.427, respectively. In table 1 and table 2, it can be shown that student trying to reduce amount of waste by collecting materials recycled, not using plastic bag to wrap things, conserving the use of electric energy, and composting the food residue to become fertilizer have significantly positive association with student having noble values of sustainability of 0.761, 0.618, 0.641, and 0.160. However, the association between student conserving the use of water supply and student having noble values of sustainability of 0.073 was not supported in this study. These study results were similar to the study found that student perception on the sustainability values in student everyday lives stimulated the environmental awareness of the students (Hassan, 2010). However, this finding was not similar to the study found that water supply conservation was positively associated with noble values of sustainability (Hassan, Noordin, Sulaiman, 2010). The structural model is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. The structural model

5. Conclusion

Environmental awareness model for students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia offered in this research is a fit model. Student having noble values of sustainability are positively associated with student environmental awareness. However, the associations between student environmental practices and student environmental attitudes with the student environmental awareness were not supported in this study. It can be concluded that the model of environmental awareness hypothesized in this study can be implemented for students at Universitas Negeri Jakarta in Indonesia focusing on the relationship between student having noble values of sustainability and student environmental awareness.

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